

The Effects of Interlayered Carbon Nanotube Reinforced Electrospun Nanofibers on Mixed Mode Fracture Characteristics

Ozge Kaynan^{1,3}, Yagmur Atescan^{2,3}, Sassan Jahangiri¹, Hulya Cebeci^{2,3,*}, Elif Ozden-Yenigun^{1,3}

¹ Department of Textile Engineering, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul 34437, Turkey

² Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul 34469, Turkey

³ ITU Aerospace Research Center, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, 34469, Turkey

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*Corresponding Author

E-mail: geyikh@itu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Stability and stiffness of interface region have significant impact on mechanical properties in laminated composites; however, their performances suffer from layer separation and/or delamination. Nanofiber interlayered interface structures are promising approaches to improve resistance to failure. The goal of this study is to investigate the effect of incorporation of CNT reinforced electrospun nanofibrous mats on the interlaminar properties of laminated composites through identifying mixed mode delamination mechanism within simulating genuine loading conditions. Electrospinning method was preferred to fabricate homogeneous and adhesive polyvinyl butral (PVB)/CNTs networks to interlaminar at mid-plane of composite with no weight penalty. The effect of electrospun nanofibrous mats on interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fiber prepreg reinforced composites were investigated by using various CNTs weight fractions (such as 0.5, 1, 2 %) in nanofibrous mats. The fractography images revealed that electrospun nanofibers were distributed homogeneously at interface while improving energy dissipation in-plane and through laminate thickness. The results also pointed out that neat laminates showed essentially linear load increase after crack propagation whereas nano-interlayered composites exhibited nonlinear and irregular load drops due to the effect of adhesive interleaving. It is evident that all nanofiber interlayers were effective in retardation of crack propagation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delaying or preventing delamination has a crucial importance on the load bearing capability and lifetime of the composite structures [1]. Besides widely known proper lay-up sequence to minimize interlaminar stresses and stitching, novel approaches such as tailoring the interlaminar regions using nanofibers between two subsequent plies are considered. Since these interfacial regions are resin rich, adding sub-phases in these planes is proposed to retard crack propagation and the mechanism is referred as interlayer toughening [2-5]. Having an ease on implementation of these interlayers in the composites makes them also promising candidates for investigation of nanoscale morphology effects and toughening strategies on the fracture toughness of laminated structures. Electrospinning is one of the efficient methods for distribution of fibers through the polymer composite surface homogeneously [5-8]. PVB resin is considered as providing strong adhesion to polymer surfaces such as epoxy/carbon fiber, and combination of PVB with CNTs is promising for strong interface, where CNTs act as nano pins which may resist to fracture delamination [1]. Hence, electrospinning would be the effective technique to disperse CNTs individually by applied electrical field and to align them in PVB polymer host.

The fracture delamination resistance of nanofiber interlayered composites under quasi-static loads were widely studied [9-11]. Instead of applying solely mode I and mode II loadings for investigation of crack initiating, mixed mode I+II bending test provides more realistic conditions [12] and enables to determine interlaminar fracture toughness (G_c) and work with various loading ratios [13-16]. Yayla *et al.* [17] investigated fracture morphology of carbon fiber reinforced composites

under mode I, mode II and mixed mode I+II loadings. The results demonstrated that the delamination failure was initiated in matrix and interphase region for mode I and mode II loadings whereas direction of plastically deformed fibers change related to loading ratio, which indicates the importance of loading ratio for examination of delamination of laminated composite. Hence, applying mixed mode I+II would provide remarkable consequences for toughening mechanism and fracture surface traces.

Herein, we aim to investigate the effects of adhesive PVB/CNTs nanofibrous network interlayered composites under mixed mode I+II loadings compared to neat laminates. CNTs reinforced PVB is electrospun through the carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg to obtain a strong adhesive layer for interlaminar toughness. Due to intermolecular interaction between PVB/CNTs, CNTs disperse homogeneously through PVB nanofiber, which improves reinforcement and binding the structural laminates. Moreover, chemical compatibility of PVB leads to excellent epoxy wetting, which results in well adhesion between nanofiber and layers of the laminate. The contribution of CNTs on fracture toughness are investigated by different weight fractions such as 0.5, 1 and 2 wt %, respectively. Crack propagation of composites are examined under mixed mode bending test and the results revealed that CNTs reinforced nanofiber composites demonstrated increase in both crack length and fracture energy release.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In this study, neat and interlaminated composites were fabricated. Toughening of laminates were performed by electrospun PVB/CNTs where PVB (Butvar®, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 10 wt % methanol (Sigma Aldrich) and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (purity 95%, nominal diameter 6-9 nm, length 5 μ) were then added to the solution with 0.5, 1 and 2 wt % of the polymer content by magnetic stirring for 24 hours. No surface modification or purification was employed to chemicals used in this work. As seen in Fig.1, the PVB/CNTs solution was directly electrospun through the surface of 2x2 carbon fiber/epoxy prepregs (SPM Composite Advanced Materials Technologies Company, VTP H310 resin system). Electrospinning process parameters are 15 kV voltage applied, 0.5mL/hr solution flow rate and 15 cm distance from tip to ground. Following to electrospinning process, nanofibrous mat with mean fiber diameter of 130-200 nm was completely impregnated by carbon fiber prepreg surface.

Mixed mode bending test specimens were fabricated by 16 plies of carbon/epoxy prepregs to reach specified thickness regarding to ASTM-D6671 [16]. Nanofibrous embedded carbon prepreg was placed on the mid-layer where release film was also located the rest for interlaminated composites. Base laminates also include release film at mid-plane to initiate crack propagation. Following to fabrication of laminates ply by ply, the stacks was placed on a metallic tooling plate with laying release film, peel ply and nonwoven breather layer. Both heating and vacuum effect were applied at the same time to the prepreg stacks during curing cycle, at which 150°C for 2 hr under -1 atm. Mixed mode test specimens were prepared by hinged two sides with adhesive glue which is displayed in Fig 2.

Fig.1 Electrospinning process

Fig. 2 Mixed mode test specimen

The characterization of CNTs/PVB nanofibers and fracture surface morphologies were measured by 15 keV secondary electrons in field emission gun equipped scanning electron microscope (SEM). Electrospun nanofiber diameters were evaluated by ImageJ software and the mean fiber diameter and distribution calculated by at least 40 measurements from randomly selected fibers.

Mixed mode bending is a combination of double cantilever beam (mode I) and end notch flexure (mode II). In this work, modal ratio of neat and interlaminated composites was set as 30 %, which was evaluated by $(G_{II}/(G_I+G_{II}))$ where G_I and G_{II} are mode I and mode II strain energy release rates.

The lever length c was evaluated by Eq.1 where α is the mode mixture transformation parameter for setting the lever length, β is the non-dimensional crack length correction parameter and L is the half span length. α and β are calculated by Eq.2 and Eq. 3, respectively. Eq. 4 is formula of crack length correction parameter which is calculated as 1.45, where E_{11} is longitudinal modulus of elasticity, G_{13} is out of plane shear modulus for carbon fiber prepreps. Transfer modulus correction parameter Γ derived by Eq. 5, where E_{22} is the transfer modulus of elasticity. The values of E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{13} for 2x2 bidirectional prepreg were set as 100, 100 and 5 GPa and c was specified as 90mm. The displacement rate of all tests was 0.5 mm/min.

$$c = \frac{12\beta^2 + 3\alpha + 8\beta\sqrt{3\alpha}}{36\beta^2 - 3\alpha} L \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1 - \frac{G_{II}}{G}}{\frac{G_{II}}{G}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\beta = \frac{\alpha + \chi h}{\alpha + 0.42\chi h} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}}{11G_{13}} \left\{ 3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{1 + \Gamma} \right)^2 \right\}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\Gamma = 1.18 \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}E_{22}}{G_{13}}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The mixed mode strain energy release G_C is the sum of G_I and G_{II} , which are calculated by Eq. 6 and 7. The modulus of elasticity E_{1f} is derived by Eq. 8 where P is load applied, α is the total debonding length, b is width of the specimen α_0 is initial delamination length, m is the slope of the force displacement curve and C_{sys} is the system compliance.

$$G_I = \frac{12P^2(3c - L)^2}{16b^2h^3L^2E_{1f}} (\alpha + \chi h)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2(c + L)^2}{16b^2h^3L^2E_{1f}} (\alpha + 0.42\chi h)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$E_{1f} = \frac{8(\alpha_0 + \chi h)^3(3c - L)^2 + [6(\alpha_0 + 0.42\chi h)^3 + 4L^3](c + L)^2}{16L^2bh^3 \left(\frac{1}{m} - C_{sys} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PVB polymer has a strong capability of effective binding and polymer surface adhesion for r engineering applications. There are several attempts to produce CNTs incorporated PVB resin applications [10,21]. Applying electrospinning to the CNTs included polymer solutions is a challenging process since dissolution of CNTs in the solution and ensuring homogeneous formation of suspension is hard to obtain. Hence, intermolecular interactions of PVB/CNTs affects dispersion of nanoparticles and polymer re-aggration, which presence of repulsive force between PVB and CNTs and electro-hydrodynamic spinning lead to effective dispersion of nanotubes in polymer without precipitation. In this study, the goal is to fabricate adhesive layers reinforced with micron scale CNTs and integrate the layers into structural laminated composites. Both adhesive PVB and stiff CNTs would assist to improve fracture toughness of laminates against to mixed mode I and II delamination, and result in crack retardation, as well as increase in mixed mode release energy and crack propagation length.

Fig. 3 a) 0.5 wt %, b) 1 wt % and c) 2 wt % CNTs reinforced nanofiber SEM images

Fig. 3 a-c demonstrates the morphology of PVB/CNTs electrospun nanofibers, in which each were fabricated with the constant parameters at 15 kV, 0.5 μ l/hr flow rate, and 15 cm distance. Increase of CNTs weight content leads to a decrease in mean fiber diameter from 201 \pm 8 nm to 131 \pm 8 nm due to reduction in viscosity and rheological variations in polymer solution. It is also worth to note that web homogeneity was not disturbed by CNTs incorporation which did not create bead-like formation and nanotubes agglomeration. Moreover, applied curing temperature (150 $^{\circ}$ C) was much above T_g of PVB (71 $^{\circ}$ C) which resulted in nanofibrous web structure and CNTs dispersion in adhesive network.

The impacts of CNTs nanofibrous incorporation on crack propagation and delamination growth under mixed mode load were investigated. As **Fig. 4** displays, the presence of CNT reinforced adhesive layer in the laminated composites leads to an increase in irregular and nonlinear load cycles following to crack reinitiation as exhibited all CNT interlayered composites (0.5, 1 and 2 wt %) while neat composites demonstrated a linear load increase. The multiple load drops observed in CNT interlayered laminates resists much higher crack length, which indicates a fracture resistance mechanism and good interfacial bonding. Besides, all interlayered specimen arrested and retarded the crack propagation at around 5 mm, which was pointed in **Fig.4**. 1 wt % CNTs nanofiber interlayered composite resulted in 12% increase in maximum load compared to neat laminates. However, 2 wt % CNTs incorporated laminates showed slight decrease in load, but still displayed high G_C and increased crack length. Moreover, resistance to crack growth was observed for all nano-interlayered laminates; hence, this leads to higher dissipation energy. Neat composites resisted cracks up to 40 mm whereas nano-interlayered laminates restrained crack initiation up to 55 mm. Also, average G_C of specimens at fracture interpreted as 1.16 \pm 0.09, 1.88 \pm 0.2 and 1.15 \pm 0.1 kJ/m² for 0.5, 1 and 2 wt % CNTs interlayered composites while 0.6 \pm 0.005 kJ/m² for neat laminates. As a result, the consequences suggested a single layer of CNTs reinforced nanofiber toughening leads to increase in G_C and crack delamination length.

Fig. 4 Load versus displacement relation for both neat and all nano-interlayered composites and black arrow refers crack initiation in neat composite which is eliminated by interlaminated composites

Fig. 5 exhibits fracture surface images of neat and CNT interlayered composites after MMB testing. **Fig. 5 a** represents neat surface which exhibits both cusps and fiber bridging referring to mode I and II delamination failure. Smooth fracture surface of neat composites indicates low crack growth resistance resulted in uninterrupted crack initiation through epoxy matrix. However, CNTs incorporated laminates revealed traces in fracture surface due to larger interacted surface area, which

can be seen in **Fig. 5 b-c**. **Fig 5 b** points out adhesive failure of single nanofiber interlayered composite ply layer, which addresses well adhesion polymer and fiber surface. It is noteworthy that **Fig 5 c** demonstrates apparently a change in surface roughness of adhesive nanofiber and showed pull-off nanofiber, indicating fiber bridging during loading. Also, it is clear that how adhesive network covers the individual fibers in the surface of laminate.

Fig. 5 Fracture surface SEM images of **a)** neat, **b)** CNTs nanofibrous interlayered composites and **c)** zoomed view of (b) demonstrate well adhesion between fiber and epoxy surface.

4 CONCLUSION

Fracture toughness of bidirectional carbon prepreg laminates have been investigated where the crack propagated at mid-layer reinforced with CNTs/PVB adhesive nanofiber under mixed mode I and II loading. This study also explored fracture delamination mechanism of CNTs reinforced PVB beyond T_g resulted in adhesive nanofibrous network. Mixed mode bending tests demonstrated that neat laminates revealed linear load following to crack initiation while CNTs incorporated composites showed crack retardation and nonlinearity in the load increase drops due to the presence of adhesive interlayer. Beside, crack length increased up to 55 mm by incorporation of CNTs reinforced nanofibers in the laminated structure compared to neat composites which was 40 mm. Beside, due to the resistance provided by PVB/CNTs adhesive layer, G_C is also raised, which reached $1.88 \pm 0.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ at fracture for 1 wt % CNTs reinforced laminates. Fracture surface studies also pointed out the effect of CNTs incorporated nanofibrous interlaminar on retardation of delamination because of the presence of stiff CNTs and adhesive PVB nanofibrous network.

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